

Chemistry of some ruthenium phenolates. Synthesis, characterization and redox properties

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Reaction of phenols containing a second donor site linked to the *ortho*-position [viz. 2,4,6-tribromophenol (HL¹), 2-nitrophenol (HL²) and 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (HL³)] with [Ru(bpy)₂Cl₂] in the presence of a base has afforded complexes of the type [Ru(bpy)₂(L)]⁺ (where L stands for the deprotonated ligands), which have been isolated as perchlorate salts in the solid state. The complexes are diamagnetic (low-spin *d*⁶, *S* = 0) and in solution show several MLCT transitions in the visible region. Cyclic voltammetry of the [Ru(bpy)₂(L)]⁺ complexes in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TEAP) shows a Ru^{II}-Ru^{III} oxidation within 0.63 to 0.93 V vs SCE and one reduction of the coordinated bpy within -1.42 to -1.68 V vs SCE.

The present work originated from our interest in the chemistry of ruthenium complexed by phenolic ligands¹. Coordination of ruthenium by phenolate oxygen is of current interest with particular reference to stability of higher oxidation states of this metal². Phenolic ligands of type 1, where D is a second donor atom incorporated at the *ortho*-position via one or two intervening atoms, have been chosen as the principal ligand for the present study. The ligands are abbreviated in general as HL, where H stands

for the dissociable phenolic proton. Ligands of this type are known to bind to metal ion, via dissociation of the phenolic proton, as bidentate ligands forming five- and six-membered chelate rings^{1,2}. The present study has been restricted to complexes of ruthenium containing only one phenolate ligand. To satisfy the remaining four coordination sites of ruthenium in this RuL moiety, 2,2'-bipyridine (bpy, 2) has been used as the coligand. The synthesis, characterization and cyclic voltammetric studies of a group of [Ru(bpy)₂(L)]⁺ complexes are reported here.

Results and Discussion

Three phenolic ligands, viz. 2,4,6-tribromophenol (HL¹, 3), 2-nitrophenol (HL², 4) and 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (HL³, 5), have been used. Three complexes of type

[Ru(bpy)₂(L)]⁺ (Table 1) have been synthesized in good yields by following a general route as shown in eq. (1),

The complex cations have been isolated as perchlorate salts in the solid state. The observed elemental (C, H, N) analytical data are in good agreement with the compositions of the complexes. 2,4,6-Tribromophenol is known to coordinate to a metal ion as a bidentate O,Br-donor forming five-membered chelate ring (6)³. 2-Nitrophenol is reported to coordinate as a bidentate O,O-donor forming six-membered chelate ring (7)⁴ and 2,4,6-trinitrophenol is known to form similar six-membered chelate ring (8)⁵. As 2,2'-bipyridine is a symmetrical bidentate ligand, the question of geometrical isomerism does not arise in these

[Ru(bpy)₂(L)]ClO₄ complexes. The IR spectra of the [Ru(bpy)₂(L)]ClO₄ complexes are complicated, due to vibrations arising from bpy, L and ClO₄. Assignment of all the individual bands has not been attempted. However, comparison of the observed spectra with that of [Ru(bpy)₂Cl₂] affords useful information. For example, the $\nu_{\text{Ru-Cl}}$ stretches observed at 315 and 330 cm⁻¹ in [Ru(bpy)₂Cl₂] are absent in [Ru(bpy)₂(L)]ClO₄, as expected. Strong vibrations observed near 1100 and 620 cm⁻¹ in all the [Ru(bpy)₂(L)]ClO₄ complexes are attributable to the perchlorate ion. The spectra of [Ru(bpy)₂Cl₂] and the [Ru(bpy)₂(L)]ClO₄ complexes show many common bands (such as 1600, 1480, 1440, 1400 and 760 cm⁻¹) which are obviously due to the common Ru(bpy)₂ fragment. The IR spectral data are therefore in accordance with the composi-

tions of these complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements show that the $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L})]\text{ClO}_4$ complexes are diamagnetic, which corresponds to the +2 oxidation state of ruthenium (low-spin d^6 , $S = 0$). The $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L})]\text{ClO}_4$ complexes are soluble in common polar organic solvents such as acetonitrile, acetone, dichloromethane, producing intense red solutions. Conductivity measurement in acetonitrile solution shows that the complexes behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes ($\lambda_M = 140\text{--}155 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), as expected. Electronic spectral data of the complexes (Table 1) show absorptions in the visible and ultraviolet regions. The absorptions observed in the UV region are of very high intensity, attributable to transitions within the ligand orbitals. The intense absorptions observed in the visible region are probably due to allowed metal-to-ligand charge-transfer transitions. Multiple charge-transfer transitions in these mixed ligand complexes may result from lower symmetry splitting of the metal level, the presence of different acceptor orbitals and from the mixing of singlet and triplet configurations in the excited state through spin-orbit coupling⁶.

Table 1. Microanalytical, electronic spectral and cyclic voltammetric data*

Compd	λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	$E_{1/2}$, V (ΔE_p , mV) ^{a,b}
$[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L}^1)]\text{ClO}_4$	473(1600), 330(2400), 292(10000), 246(5500)	0.63(100), -1.68
$[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L}^2)]\text{ClO}_4$	472(2000), 347(2200), 291(11600), 245(7600)	0.78(120), -1.62
$[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L}^3)]\text{ClO}_4$	460 ^c (3800), 376(4900), 286(10000), 243(6400)	0.93(110), -1.42

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

^aIn acetonitrile solution. ^b $E_{1/2} = 0.5(E_{pa} + E_{pc})$, where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials respectively; $\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$; solute concentration, $10^{-3}M$, scan rate, 50 mV s^{-1} . ^cShoulder

Cyclic voltammetric studies: Electron-transfer properties of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L})]\text{ClO}_4$ complexes have been studied in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TEAP) by cyclic voltammetry. Voltammetric data are presented in Table 1 and a representative voltammogram is displayed in Fig. 1. Each complex shows two voltammetric responses, one oxidative response on the positive side of SCE and the other reductive response on the negative side. The oxidative response, observed within 0.63 to 0.93 V (all potentials are referred to SCE), is assigned to the $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\text{-Ru}^{\text{III}}$ oxidation (eq. 2),

This oxidation is quasi-reversible for all the complexes characterized by a peak-to-peak separation (ΔE_p) of 100–120 mV. The one-electron nature of this oxidation has been

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L}^2)]\text{ClO}_4$ in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TEAP) at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1}

established by comparing its current height with that of standard ferrocene/ferrocenium couple under identical experimental conditions. In $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$, the $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\text{-Ru}^{\text{III}}$ oxidation takes place at 1.30 V⁷. In the present $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L})]\text{ClO}_4$ complexes the same oxidation takes place at much lower potential, which may be attributed to coordination by the phenolate oxygen. One reductive response is exhibited by all the $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L})]^+$ complexes within -1.42 V to -1.68 V which is assigned to reduction of one coordinated bpy ligand (eq. 3),

It is well documented in the literature that each bpy can successively accept two electrons in its lowest unoccupied molecular orbital⁸. Hence in these $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L})]^+$ complexes four successive reductions may be expected, of which only one has been experimentally observed. The other reductive responses could not be observed due to the solvent cut-off.

Experimental

Commercial ruthenium trichloride (Arora Matthey, India) was converted to $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by repeated evaporation with conc. HCl. 2,2'-Bipyridine and *cis*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{Cl}_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were synthesized using the reported procedure⁹. 2,4,6-Tribromophenol, 2-nitrophenol and 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (S.D. Fine Chemicals, India) were used. Purification of acetonitrile and preparation of tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP) were performed as reported in the literature¹⁰. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and used as received.

Preparation of complexes. General method.
 $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{L}^3)]\text{ClO}_4$: A mixture of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{Cl}_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (100 mg, 0.19 mmol) dissolved in ethanol (40 cm^3) and AgNO_3 (65 mg, 0.38 mmol) was stirred for 30 min. The deposited AgCl was separated by filtration and to the

filtrate was added 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (HL³) (44 mg, 0.19 mmol) and NaOH (8 mg, 0.20 mmol). The resulting red solution was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and a saturated aqueous solution of NaClO₄ (0.2 cm³) was added. [Ru(bpy)₂(L³)]ClO₄ precipitated as a brownish red crystalline solid, which was washed with cold water, dried under reduced pressure over P₄O₁₀ and crystallized from 1 : 1 acetonitrile-benzene as dark red microcrystals (140 mg, 78%).

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrometer and electronic spectra (acetonitrile) on a Shimadzu UV 240 spectrophotometer. Solution electrical conductivity was measured using a Philips PR9500 bridge with a solute concentration of about 10⁻³ M. Magnetic susceptibility was measured using a PAR 155 magnetometer fitted with a Walker scientific L75FBAL magnet. Electrochemical measurements were made using a PAR 273 potentiostat. A platinum disc working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and an aqueous saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) were used in a three-electrode configuration. A RE 0089 X-Y recorder was used to trace the voltammograms. Dinitrogen gas was purified by bubbling it successively through alkaline dithionite and concentrated sulfuric acid. All electrochemical experiments were performed under dinitrogen atmosphere. All electrochemical data were collected at 298 K and are uncorrected for junction potentials.

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